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CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR DUAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the main objectives and intended outcomes of a Erasmus + Project *Towards Excellence in Engineering Curricula for Dual Education* (TEEDE) coordinated by the University Rovira i Virgili (URV, Spain). The project has received funding under the Key Action 2: Capacity building in the field of higher education. This joint multi-country project including partners from Europe, Russia, China, India and Cambodia aims to promote the modernization, to expand the availability and to develop the internationalization of higher education in the partner countries: to promote intercultural and interpersonal exchange, and to promote the voluntary convergence with the tendencies of the development of higher education in the EU.

The main output of the project will be upgraded/developed curricula in engineering trades. It will be possible through development of methodological guidelines on professions and qualifications based on the analysis of the economic needs of the different regions involved.

Conference Key Areas: University-Business cooperation, Curriculum Development

Keywords: dual education, engineering education, curriculum development, university - industry cooperation

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INTRODUCTION

Today many countries all over the world are seeking ways to strengthen the linkages among employers, workers, higher education institutions, and governments. One of the possible ways to meet this challenge is dual education. In this system, training for industrial trades is a shared responsibility of firms and schools. Trainees divide their time roughly equally between classroom and on-the-job training, with both pathways developed in parallel. As trainees, they (might) receive a lower wage than regular workers, but are guaranteed secure, well-paid jobs at the firm upon successful completion of the program and receiving of a certificate [1].

1 WHAT IS DUAL EDUCATION

Even a preliminary literature review [2,3,4] reveals a lot of distinctive features how dual education is understood and implemented in different countries. The variation in the details is not relevant for the purpose of this paper, as we will refer to the context of the TEEDE project [5], which determines the most important characteristics of the dual system as the following:

- Combines apprenticeships in a company and formal education in the same course.
- Students are workers of the company.
- Students have some sort of labor contract.

This means that perform an internship or develop the final year project in a company is not considered as a dual education, as the involvement of the companies are more superficial

Crucial to the system's effectiveness is the close collaboration of industry and higher education institutions. If we manage to establish/reinforce this kind of cooperation, then it will provide important advantages for all stakeholders:

- Labor contract.
- Development of apprentices under real conditions.
- Apprentices benefits also from coworkers knowledge.
- Hard and soft skills are simultaneously developed in the company environment.
- Facilitates school-to-work transition.
- Improved retention for employer.

The limitations for successful implementation of such a system could be:

- Training is more expensive than the school-based approach.
- Companies have to follow many regulations
- Companies are often specialized and unable to train apprentices in all areas and with the broad view of a master (e.g., small and medium enterprises).
- More student effort required, as they have to combine both tasks.
- Organizational changes are required also for Universities, which are not characterized by fast response times and actions.

In order to share best European practices and to make dual system more widespread in engineering education in such regions as Asia and Russia the Erasmus + project *Towards Excellence in Engineering Curricula for Dual Education (TEEDE)* has started

in October 2016 [5]. The project has received funding under the Key Action 2: Capacity building in the field of higher education. This joint multi-country project including partners from Europe, Russia, China, India and Cambodia aims to:

- Promote the modernization
- Expand the availability and to develop the internationalization of higher education in the partner countries
- Promote intercultural and interpersonal exchange
- Foster the voluntary convergence with the tendencies of the development of higher education in the EU.

2 TEEDE PROJECT

2.1 Consortium

The TEEDE project consortium consists of:

- University Rovira i Virgili (Universitat Rovira i Virgili): URV, Spain. Project Coordinator.
- University of Tampere (Tampereen Yliopisto): UTA, Finland.
- Institute Technology and Education (Universitaet Bremen): ITB, Germany.
- University of Pavia (Universita Degli Studi di Pavia): UNIPV, Italy.
- Tomsk Polytechnic University: TPU, Russia.
- Far Eastern Federal University: FEFU, Russia.
- Katanov Khakass State University: KHSU, Russia.
- Omsk State University: OSIS, Russia.
- Jilin University: JLU, China.
- Shenyang Ligong University: SYLU, China.
- Institute de Technologie du Cambodge: ITC, Cambodia.
- Royal University of Agriculture: RUA, Cambodia.
- Indian Institute of Technology Madras: IITM, India.
- The Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur: IITK, India
- European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education: ENQA, Belgium.
- Association for Engineering Education of Russia: AEER, Russia.

All partners of the consortium have a strong focus on technology and engineering and serve as regional centres for implementation of national strategies for training professionals. The problem of training professionals for the real sector of economy has emerged due to immense development of high technologies, shortening the period from development to implementation, growing technological needs of the society. As a result there exist a need for new approaches to the development of curricula sensitive and flexible to demands of companies based on innovations. This challenge is common for all regions involved in implementation of the project: EU, Russia and Asia.

2.2 Objectives

To meet this challenge in the course of the project partners will:

1. Identify needs, select key professions and areas of training.
2. Develop and modernize curricula implementing the principles of the dual education under the guidance of European experts.
3. Launch new or upgraded curricula, combining periods of study with periods of

- training at leading enterprises.
4. Create a system of continuous professional development.
 5. Create communication and recourse centres at partner universities.

The specific objectives of the TEEDE project are the:

- Modernization and creation of the bachelor and master's degree programs in engineering based on the European principles of dual education;
- Development and implementation of the methodology of management of educational processes in universities following the dual education approach;
- Strengthening relations of universities with exterior economic and social environment, creation and development of variants of the cooperation of universities and enterprises, promotion of employment of graduates;
- Creation of communication and recourse centers for promotion of the projects results and further implementation of the project's outputs beyond the project cycle period;
- Establishment of the unified procedure of evaluation of qualification level achieved by the persons who are studying in engineering and the recognition of learning;
- Construction of the trajectory of lifelong learning for the engineers.

2.3 Outputs

The main output of the TEEDE project will be upgraded/developed curricula in engineering trades. It will be possible through development of methodological guidelines on professions and qualifications based on the analysis of the economic needs of three regions.

These outputs will be available to all stakeholders through the created communication and resource centres as well as the project website and through open communication of the partners that secures the reliability and high quality of the project outcomes.

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